

THE CHEMISTRY OF SOME DERIVATIVES OF DECALIN. PART I.

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On oxidation with selenium dioxide, *trans*- β -decalone yields a diketone which is proved to be 2:3-diketo-*trans*-decalin. On monobromination, the decalone yields 2-keto-3-bromo-*trans*-decalin, the bromine atom of which is very inert to the usual reagents. The dibromo compound obtained from decalone, which yields with alkali hexahydrohydrindenol- β -carboxylic acid, is most probably 2-keto-3:3-dibromo-*trans*-decalin. 2:3-Diketo-*trans*-decalin yields on reduction (a) the corresponding dihydroxy compound, m. p. 141°, with sodium amalgam and (b) another isomeric dihydroxy compound, m. p. 126°, with aluminium amalgam. The stereochemistry of the dihydroxy-*trans*-decalins is discussed and it is suggested that the above two compounds have the hydroxy groups in the *trans*-positions.

Wallach and Wissenborn (*Annalen*, 1924, 487, 153) treated the dibromo compound furnished by the bromination of decalone (which we now consider to be *cis* from its physical constants n_D , 1.49317 and d^{19} , 1.0055) with aqueous potash and obtained (besides other acidic products*) two diketones, m. p. 88-89°, and m. p. 99-100°. The former, which was the main product, was proved by them to be 2:3-diketodecalin (which we now consider to be *cis*), while the latter, obtained in small yields, was not thoroughly investigated. It was suggested to be an isomer (*i.e.* 1:2-diketodecalin) or a "diketone of a lower hydrogenation product." Recently, Rao and Kuppusamy (*J. Annamalai Univ.*, 1937, 7, 23) oxidised *trans*- β -decalone with selenium dioxide and obtained two fractions: (i) b. p. 106-108°/6 mm. and (ii) b. p. 126-30°/6 mm. The former was considered by them to be the diketone (1:2 or 2:3) of *trans*-decalin, while the second fraction was not investigated.

trans- β -Decalone was smoothly oxidised by selenium dioxide in boiling alcohol to yield a crystalline solid, m. p. 99-100°, which has now been proved to be 2:3-diketo-*trans*-decalin (I) by the following properties and reactions: (i) it is colourless and forms an enol benzoate and exhibits the properties of the diosphenol form (II) (*cf.* Robinson, "The Electronic Theory of the

* The dibasic acid, $C_{10}H_{16}O_4$, obtained by the authors, is probably *cis*-cyclohexane-1:2-diacetic acid (m. p. 159-61°); but the high melting point (165°) recorded by them is probably due to an error. It is not likely that this acid can be the *trans* isomer (m. p. 167°) because the starting decalone is predominantly *cis* and an isomerisation to *trans* form during the reaction is very remote.

Course of Organic Reactions," Institute of Chemistry, 1932, p. 30-31); it also shows the absorption maximum at $2689\text{\AA}^*$ characteristic of the α -diketones; (ii) with hydrogen peroxide it yields *trans*-cyclohexane-1:2-diacetic acid; (iii) with sodium amalgam, a mixture of 2:3-dihydroxy-*trans*-decalin and 2-keto-3-hydroxy-*trans*-decalin is obtained (*cf.* Lehmann and Kraetschell, *Ber.*, 1934, 67, 1867) and (iv) by boiling with sodium hydroxide it is converted into *trans*-hexahydrohydrindenol- β -carboxylic acid (III). This acid (III) has been obtained by Lehmann and Kraetschell (*Ber.*, 1935, 68, 360) by boiling 2-keto-3-chloro-*trans*-decalin or 2-keto-3:3-dichloro-*trans*-decalin (*vide infra*) with alkali, the formation of the diketone (I) being postulated by them to be the intermediate in the reactions. The diketone (I) condenses with 4:5-diaminouracil and 4:5-diaminothiouracil to furnish in good yields 2':3'-*trans*-decalolumazine (IV, R=O) and 2':3'-*trans*-decalothiolumazine (IV, R=S) respectively.

(I)

(II)

(III)

(IV)

It is now evident that the diketone, m. p. $99-100^\circ$, of Wallach and Wissenborn (*loc. cit.*) is 2:3-diketo-*trans*-decalin, probably formed by the contamination of their (*cis*) decalone with a small quantity of the *trans*-variety; the isomerisation of the *cis*-diketone (m. p. $88-89^\circ$) to the *trans* form (I) is not probable since the keto groups concerned in this compound are in the β -positions and the conditions of its formation are not likely to cause such an isomerisation (*cf.* Hückel *et al.*, *Annalen*, 1927, 481, 109; 1930, 502, 99; Cook and Linstead, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 946).

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Though during halogenations and condensation reactions only the carbon atom in position 3 of *trans*- β -decalone has been found to be reactive (Lehmann and Kraetschell, *loc. cit.*; Feu, McQuillon and Robinson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 53; Cook and Lawrence, *ibid.*, p.877; Errington and Linstead, *ibid.*, 1938, 669), on oxidation with nitric acid *trans*- β -decalone yields as the main product *trans*-cyclohexane-1:2-diacetic acid along with a small quantity of *trans*-cyclohexane-1-carboxy-2-propionic acid (Kandiah, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 923). But in the above oxidation of *trans*- β -decalone with selenium dioxide, no 1:2-diketo-*trans*-decalin could be detected. In this connection, it should be of interest to note that Stiller and Rosenheim (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 353) by the oxidation of (3)-cholestanone with selenium dioxide could isolate only 2:3-diketocholestane.*

Rao and Kuppusamy (*loc. cit.*) brominated *trans*- β -decalone and obtained a monobromo compound which was considered by them to be 1- or 3-bromo-2-keto-*trans*-decalin.† As was pointed above, the substitutions in the case of either *cis*- or *trans*- β -decalone always take place at the carbon atom 3 so that we should expect this bromo compound to be 2-keto-3-bromo-*trans*-decalin. In attempting to verify this by the hydrolysis of the bromoketone to the corresponding known hydroxy compound, it was found that the bromine atom concerned was very inert to alkali and even the ketonic property of the compound was masked. Whereas the 3-chloro derivatives of both *cis*- and *trans*- β -decalones are readily hydrolysed by boiling with 1% sodium hydroxide solution (Lehmann and Kraetschell, *loc. cit.*; Cook and Lawrence, *loc. cit.*) and 2:3-dibromo-*trans*-decalin with 2% potash (Leroux, *Ann. chim. phys.*, 1910, viii, 21, 496), the bromoketone was not hydrolysed even to an appreciable extent under these conditions. A trace of a product could be isolated which appeared to be identical with 2-keto-3-hydroxy-*trans*-decalin. It also remained unchanged by silver nitrate in boiling pyridine solution (*cf.* Dane, Wang and Schulte, *Z. physiol. Chem.*, 1936, 256, 87; Heilbron, Jones and Spring, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 801; Heilbron, Jackson, Jones and Spring, *ibid.*, 1938, 102). On heating with potassium acetate and acetic acid in a sealed tube, the bromoketone did not yield the corresponding $\alpha\beta$ -unsaturated ketone but a small amount of it appeared to isomerise to a compound (m.p. 122°) which on boiling with alkali changed back to the original bromoketone. Such an inertness of the bromine atom of this compound has, however, a

* We had just started this work as a natural sequel, when the paper of Stiller and Rosenheim appeared.

† The work was pursued in this direction because Rao and Kuppusamy have stated in their paper that neither of them will be able to continue the work.

parallel in the case of some of the bromoketones of the cholane group. Whereas the 4-bromo-(3)-ketones of the normal (*cis*-) series are easily debrominated in very good yields by boiling pyridine and also hydrolysed by methyl alcoholic potash, the 2-bromoketones of the *allo* (*trans*) series, e.g., *allopregnanedione*, 3-keto-*bis-norallocholanic acid*, *cholestanone*, etc. are debrominated only with great difficulty in very poor yields (Butenandt and Mamoli, *Ber.*, 1935, 68, 1850, 1854; Butenandt and Wolff, *ibid.*, p. 2091; Butenandt and Dannenberg, *ibid.*, 1936, 69, 1158).

With two molecules of bromine, *trans*- β -decalone yields a dibromo compound (Rao and Kuppusamy, *loc. cit.*) which can be either 1:3-dibromo-2-keto-*trans*-decalin or 3:3-dibromo-2-keto-*trans*-decalin (VI). An attempt is being made to decide between the two structures. The dibromo compound which is only very slowly acted on by shaking with 20% potash in the cold (*cf.* Wallach and Wissenborn, *loc. cit.*), on boiling for a few hours yields a mixture from which *trans*-hexahydrohydriudenol-carboxylic acid (III) has been isolated. Since the dichloro-*trans*- β -decalone on boiling with alkali furnished the same acid (III) as the sole product (92% yield), Lehmann and Kraetshell (*loc. cit.*) have suggested that the latter should be represented as 3:3-dichloro-2-keto-*trans*-decalin.

Although 1:3-dichloro-2-keto-*trans*-decalin can also yield the acid (III), it is more probable that an acid of the structure (VII) should be formed from it. Therefore by analogy we represent the dibromo compound tentatively as (VI). It is interesting to note that Inhoffen (*Ber.*, 1937, 70, 1695) definitely proved that the dibromo compound obtained by the bromination of 2-bromocholestanone (Butenandt and Schram, *Ber.*, 1936, 69, 2779) or dibromination of cholestanone (Ruzicka, Bonhard, Fischer and Wirz, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1936, 19, 1149) as the 2:4-dibromo and not 2:2-dibromocholestanone.

The 2:3-dihydroxydecalins are of great interest from the stereochemical point of view. Theoretically, a compound of such a structural formula can exist in three stereoisomeric forms, of which in the case of two the hydroxy groups occupy the *trans*- and in the third the *cis*- positions. The first two

should be resolvable whereas the third, being internally compensated, should not be resolvable. Leroux (*loc. cit.*) has obtained from 2:3-dibromo-*trans*-decalin three isomeric dihydroxy compounds: (i) m. p. 160° (obtained by boiling the dibromo compound with potash), (ii) m. p. 141° and (iii) m. p. 125° (both by the hydrolysis of the acetates furnished by the action of silver acetate on the dibromo compound). The first (m. p. 160°) which appears to be identical with the one m. p. 168° of Lehmann and Kraetschell (*loc. cit.*), has been shown by Leroux (*loc. cit.*) to give rise to an oxide on dehydration so that the hydroxy groups in this compound might be expected to occupy the *cis*-position provided no change in configuration has occurred during dehydration. The *cis* configuration of this compound in a way seems to be supported by the fact that it is the highest melting of the isomers. The compound, m. p. 141°, now obtained by the reduction of 2:3-diketo-*trans*-decalin by sodium amalgam (a condition which generally favours the formation of *trans*-compounds), does not also yield under the usual conditions the *isopropylidene* derivatives with acetone and hence appears to have the hydroxy groups in the *trans*-position (*cf.* Boeseken, *Rec. trav. chim.*, 1921, 40, 566; Jack and Rule, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 188). The third compound, m. p. 125°, has been considered by Leroux to be a mixture of the other two products since on acetylation it yielded the acetates of the other two isomers. It has now been found that the reduction of 2:3-diketo-*trans*-decalin with aluminium amalgam yields a dihydroxy compound, m. p. 126°, obviously identical with the compound (m. p. 125°) of Leroux. The product is definitely homogeneous but less stable than the two other forms. During acetylation a change in its configuration occurs. In case the isomer, m. p. 168°, has the hydroxy groups in the *cis*-position, as we naturally expect, then this isomer, m. p. 126°, should have the hydroxy groups in the *trans*-position. Further work on the stereochemical configurations of these dihydroxydecalins is in progress.

E X P E R I M E N T A L .

2:3-Diketo-*trans*-decalin.—The following method was found to work better than that described by Rao and Kuppusamy (*loc. cit.*).

To *trans*- β -decalone (20 g.) dissolved in ethyl alcohol (50 c. c.) and water (15 c. c.) was added gradually with good shaking finely powdered selenium dioxide (15 g.). The separation of selenium was much accelerated by boiling on the steam-bath, and in half an hour the red turbid liquid became clear. After boiling for 3 hours, the clear brown solution was decanted off, the selenium washed with a little alcohol and from the solution the solvent was removed as far as possible first under ordinary and then under reduced

pressure. The residue was diluted with water, chilled, extracted with ether, the ethereal extract washed, dehydrated and the solvent removed. The residue on distillation passed between 95-135°/5 mm. (most of it passing steadily at 123-25°/5 mm.) and set to a crystalline mass, yield 14-16 g. After keeping for some hours, the crystalline mass (10-12 g.) was drained off from the liquid portion and the latter on careful repeated fractionation, gave decalone, b. p. 96-98°/5 mm. (2 g.) and a higher boiling liquid which slowly deposited the crystals. No other product could be isolated.

The solid crystalline product separated from dilute alcohol in beautiful glistening leaflets, m. p. 99-100°, or from water in shining prismatic needles, m. p. 100-101°. (Found: C, 72.18; H, 8.38. $C_{10}H_{14}O_2$ requires C, 72.29; H, 8.43 per cent). It is colourless and possesses a characteristic phenolic and camphor odour. In contrast to diosphenol it goes into solution in dilute alkali only very slowly. An alcoholic solution is coloured light yellow. It is soluble in all organic solvents and less in boiling and least in cold water. With alcoholic ferric chloride it gives a red-violet colouration; it reduces Fehling's solution and alkaline permanganate.

Enolbenzoate of (II).—A solution of the diketone (0.5 g.) in pyridine (10 c. c.) was treated with benzoyl chloride (1 c. c.) drop by drop and after shaking well was set aside for about 18 hours. It was then diluted with water extracted with ether, the ethereal extract washed with sodium bicarbonate solution, water, dried and the solvent removed. The product obtained crystallises from petroleum ether in fine needles, m. p. 133°. (Found: C, 75.23; H, 6.46. $C_{17}H_{18}O_3$ requires C, 75.53; H, 6.70 per cent). It gives no colouration with ferric chloride.

Disemicarbazone.—When the diketone (0.8 g.) in methyl alcohol (10 c. c.) was mixed with an aqueous solution of semicarbazide hydrochloride (8.5 g.) and sodium acetate (1.5 g.), the semicarbazone began to separate. From hot dilute acetic acid it separated as a microcrystalline powder, m. p. 264-65°. (Found: N, 29.92. $C_{12}H_{20}O_2N_4$ requires N, 30.0 per cent). Rao and Kuppusamy (*loc. cit.*) record m. p. 257°. It is sparingly soluble in alcohol.

Dioxime.—To the diketone (0.8 g.) dissolved in little methyl alcohol was added hydroxylamine hydrochloride (0.8 g.), sodium hydroxide (2N, 15 c. c.) and the solution refluxed on the steam-bath for 20 minutes, cooled, diluted, and acidified whereby the dioxime was thrown down. It crystallised from alcohol in shining rhombic plates, m. p. 229° (decomp.). (Found: N, 14.35. $C_{10}H_{16}O_2N_2$ requires N, 14.29 per cent). An alcoholic solution of the dioxime gave with a solution of nickel sulphate, the rose-red precipitate of the nickel salt characteristic of the dioximes of the α -diketones.

The oximation by the method of Forster and Dunn (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1909, 98, 431) gave the same product and no isomeric forms could be obtained.

The reduction of the dioxime by sodium and alcohol furnished in poor yield a product which does not appear to be the corresponding diamine; however, aluminium amalgam in moist ether solution gave a product which appears to be an amine. This is being further investigated.

Quinoxaline.—The diketone (0.4 g.) and *o*-phenylenediamine (0.25 g.) in glacial acetic acid (8 c. c.) was refluxed for 2 hours, the brown-red solution cooled and diluted with water whereby the quinoxaline was precipitated (0.5 g.). This crystallised from water (charcoal) in glistening rhombic plates, m.p. 177–78°. (Found: N, 11.68. $C_{16}H_{16}N_2$ requires N, 11.77 per cent).

2':3'-*trans-Decalolumazine* (IV, R=O).—The diketone (0.8 g.) and 4:5-diaminouracil sulphate (1 g.) in glacial acetic acid (50 c. c.) and water (100 c. c.) were refluxed for 45 minutes during which the colourless solution became gradually yellow. On allowing to stand overnight the condensation product separated in fine prismatic needles, yield 0.8 g.; little more being obtainable from the mother-liquors on concentration. From dilute acetic acid it separated in clusters of fine colourless needles, m.p. about 315°. (Found: N, 20.32. $C_{14}H_{16}O_2N_4$ requires N, 20.44 per cent). It is moderately soluble in alcohol and goes gradually into solution in alkali, the solution exhibiting a blue fluorescence in a quartz lamp.

2':3'-*trans-Decalothiolumazine* (IV, R=S).—A mixture of the diketone (0.8 g.), 4:5-diaminothiouracil (1 g.), water (100 c. c.) and glacial acetic acid (50 c. c.) were refluxed for 45 minutes, and on cooling a crystalline mass (0.9 g.) separated. Recrystallising from dilute acetic acid, it was obtained as light yellow needles, m.p. 295°. (Found: N, 18.89. $C_{14}H_{16}ON_4S$ requires N, 19.44 per cent). It readily dissolves in aqueous sodium hydroxide and the solution appears to show a very feeble green fluorescence. It is desulphurised by yellow oxide of mercury.

Oxidation of the Diketone by Hydrogen Peroxide.—To the diketone (0.5 g.), dissolved in methyl alcohol (10 c. c.) and sodium hydroxide (5 c. c.; 2N) was added gradually with shaking a solution of hydrogen peroxide (5 c. c. of 30% diluted to 20 c. c.). The solution which warmed up was left aside overnight. On acidifying with hydrochloric acid, a crystalline product separated in nearly quantitative yield. Recrystallised from dilute alcohol, it had m.p. (and mixed m.p. with a sample of *trans-cyclohexane-1:2*-diacetic acid) 167°. [Found: Equiv., 100.3. $C_{10}H_{10}O_4$ (dibasic) requires Equiv., 100].

Reduction of Diketo-trans-decalin.—(i) A solution of the diketone (1 g.) in methyl alcohol (150 c.c.) and water (20 c.c.) was treated with sodium amalgam (4% ; 30 g.) and stirred well for 2 to 3 hours. The solution was then filtered, the light yellow filtrate acidified with hydrochloric acid and the alcohol removed as far as possible under reduced pressure. The residue was diluted with a little water, extracted thoroughly with ether and from the ethereal extract a solid was obtained (0.6 g.) which on fractional crystallisation from water yielded (i) a product in shining rhombic plates, m.p. 141°, identified to be 2 : 3-dihydroxy-*trans*-decalin (Found: C, 70.28 ; H, 10.32. $C_{10}H_{18}O_2$ requires C, 70.59 ; H, 10.59 per cent). and (ii) another product crystallising in needles, m. p. 134°, identified to be 2-keto-3-hydroxy-*trans*-decalin (Found : C, 71.18 ; H, 9.31. $C_{10}H_{16}O_2$ requires C, 71.43 ; H, 9.53 per cent). A small amount of tarry matter was also obtained.

The dihydroxy compound, m.p. 141°, was unchanged by standing for 24 hours with dry acetone and little sulphuric acid.

(ii) To the diketone (1 g.) dissolved in ether (200 c.c.), aluminium amalgam (1.5 g.), prepared according to Vogel, was added. Water was added to it from time to time to keep the reaction going on for about 24 hours. Then the ether was separated from the sludge, the latter extracted with ether and the combined ether extract washed, dried and on evaporation of the solvent furnished a product which crystallised from dilute alcohol in shining plates and from petrol (70-90°) in clusters of fine needles, m.p. 126°. (Found : C, 70.20 ; H, 10.29. $C_{10}H_{18}O_2$ requires C, 70.59 ; H, 10.59 per cent). This is definitely homogeneous and is evidently an isomeric 2 : 3-dihydroxy-*trans*-decalin.

trans-Hexahydrohydrindenol carboxylic Acid.—To obtain the corresponding *cis*-isomer, Wallach and Wissenborn (*loc. cit.*) heated the diketone with potash (1 : 2) in an autoclave at 120-30° for 30 minutes. Under the following conditions a quantitative yield can be obtained.

The diketone (0.5 g.) was refluxed for 3 hours with *N*-sodium hydroxide (10 c.c.), the alkaline solution thoroughly extracted with ether to remove any unchanged material, filtered and acidified whereby a solid was precipitated which was filtered and crystallised from boiling water, m.p. 133-34°. [Found : Equiv., 184.5. $C_{10}H_{16}O_3$ (monobasic) requires Equiv., 184.1].

2-Keto-3-bromo-trans-decalin.—This compound was prepared essentially according to the method of Rao and Kuppusamy (*loc. cit.*), modifications neither improving the yield nor giving immediately a crystalline product. It crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 150°. (Found : Br, 32.0. $C_{10}H_{15}OBr$ requires Br, 32.35 per cent). The residue does not appear to be homo-

geneous and no other crystalline product could so far be isolated. It did not give an oxime by the pyridine method.

On boiling the bromoketone with 10% potash for 6 hours or 35% soda solution for 2-4 hours or methyl alcoholic potash for a number of hours, no appreciable change was noticed, most of the material being recovered unchanged. By working up the mother-liquors of a number of experiments, however, a small quantity of a product, m.p. 130° (too small for further crystallisation) could be isolated which appears to be 2-keto-3-hydroxy-*trans*-decalin, since it caused no appreciable depression of the m.p. of an authentic specimen.

With silver benzoate the substance yielded a product, m.p. 122°, which on boiling with potash for a number of hours gave back the original bromo compound. On heating the bromo compound with potassium acetate and acetic acid in a sealed tube at 170-80° for 5 hours, most of the product was recovered unchanged and a small quantity of a compound, m.p. 122°, was produced. These reactions are being further studied.

Dibromo-trans-β-decalone.—The dibromo compound was obtained by the method of Rao and Kuppusamy. As the temperature of bromination is increased, the product loses the tendency to crystallise and probably isomers are also produced. The dibromo compound is only very slowly affected by 20% potash in the cold but on boiling for 3-4 hours, *trans*-hexahydrindenol carboxylic acid (m.p. and mixed m.p. with authentic sample, 134°), could be isolated from the alkaline mother-liquors. The yield of this acid, however, is low.

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